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STUDY AND ANALYSIS OF CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR IN RETAIL MARKET

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Abstract:

The aim of this study are determining the impact of the most used tools of sales promotion in retail sector such as coupons, sample, price discount and buy one get one free on consumer buying behavior from two aspects are brand switching and customer loyalty. Consumer promotions should stimulate purchases, sustain brand-name recognition, and gain audience participation. Themes are underlying messages. Media should be selected. In this way include direct mail, newspapers, magazines, television, the personal sales force, and group meetings. The duration of a sales promotion is set. The feasibility of shared sales promotions is weighed.

Keywords:

Consumer behavior, consumer purchase preference, Retail Market.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Consumer sales promotion having the objectives in which include the boosting brand awareness, increasing product trials, providing cost effective leads for the sales force (prospecting), hiking average purchases, encouraging repurchases, obtaining impulse sales, emphasizing novelty, and supplementing other promotional tools. The most desirable aim of advertising seems to remain the support of the sale of concrete merchandise, as mentioned above frequently accomplished by providing sufficient information to underpin customers' awareness of the certain product .

Figure 1: Promotional tools and techniques

2. SALES PROMOTION

Figure 2: Sales promotion

A sales promotion plan has six steps: setting goals ordinarily demand-oriented; assigning responsibility to advertising and sales managers, company departments, and/or outside specialists; outlining the overall plan including orientation, conditions, and other factors; selecting the types of sales promotion; coordinating the plan with the other elements of the promotion mix; and evaluating success or failure.

3. SETTING OBJECTIVES

Goals are generally demand-oriented. They should be related to channel members and to business and household consumers. Channel-member sales promotion has objectives in which included the gain in distribution, receiving adequate shelf space, increasing dealer enthusiasm, raising sales, and getting cooperation in sales promotion expenditures.

4. OVERALL PLAN

An overall sales promotion plan should be outlined and include a budget, orientation, conditions, media, duration and timing, and cooperative efforts. Sales promotion orientation refers to the focus channel members and its theme. Sales promotion can be oriented to either or both channel members and consumers. Channel member promotions should increase product knowledge, provide sales support, offer sales rewards, and aid cooperation and productivity. Sales promotion must be coordinated with other promotion efforts. Advertising and sales promotion plans should be integrated. The sales force should be notified of all promotions well in advance and trained to implement them.

5. OUTLINING SALES TASKS

The selling process outlines the tasks performed by the sales force.

- 1) Prospecting is generating a list of customer leads. It may be blind or involve referrals.
- 2) Approaching customers involves a pre-approach and greeting.
- 3) Customer wants are determined by asking questions.
- 4) The sales presentation includes a description of the product, its benefits, available options and models, price, associated services, and a demonstration (if necessary).
- 5) Questions are answered, involving further information and objections.
- 6) Closing the sale is getting the customer to agree to a purchase.
- 7) The follow-up after the sale ensures that the customer is satisfied, makes referrals, and makes repurchases (further leases- with Enterprises).

6. FUNCTIONS OF ADVERTISING

Three functions of advertising can be perceived. In this part, they will be demonstrated in more depth. Advertising are a process which are used by a merchandiser to inform customers . advertising comes across when launching new product or when the customer needs to be informed about the already existing one. One could also say that the main function of advertising is to provide particular information. advertising plays significant role in changing consumers' mind, gaining their attention and persuading them about qualities of the product.

7. GROWTH OF SALES PROMOTION

Variant techniques are used to increase sales by providing free samples. Despite of sales promotion plays significant role in the marketing mix this method seems to be less regarded than other parts (direct marketing, advertising). There is evidence that more than in other areas of marketing managerial positions in sales male executives dominate.

Figure 3: Growth of sales promotion

8. CONSUMER PROMOTIONS

Consumer and trade promotions are short-term marketing strategies. Consumer promotions are used by retailers to induce customers to buy products or services. Trade promotions are used by manufacturers and wholesalers to get their business buyers to purchase products for resale. Promotions contrast more long-term branding strategies used to build up the perception of value for your products or services. Percent-off discounts, free trials and samples, buy one get one free deals, rebates, premiums, ad specialties, and contests and sweepstakes are common examples of consumer sales promotions. Each specific promotion has its own strengths and weaknesses. In general, though, the intent is to market a better value proposition by lowering the price customers pay to get the same product or service previously sold at a higher price point.

Consumer promotions are a way to attract new customers and grow your customer base. This is a common objective for new companies or new product launches. Getting customers to switch brands by offering free samples and free trials is another goal. This approach limits the risk to customers when giving your product a try. Clearing out extra merchandise, combating competitor promotions and generating short-term revenue and cash flow are other common consumer promotion goals.

Figure 4: Consumer promotions

9. TRADE PROMOTIONS

Trade promotions can include some of the same approaches as consumer promotions. Retail trade refers to the business relationships between suppliers and resellers in the distribution channel. Suppliers also offer merchandise allowances, buyback agreements on unsold products, off-invoice allowances and slotting fees.

The primary purpose of trade promotions is to get trade buyers to make purchases they otherwise wouldn't. For suppliers, they are part of what is known as a push strategy to marketing. This means that along with marketing your products to consumers, you promote them to trade buyers to motivate them to carry them in stores. As a new business, for instance, it is difficult to get a retailer to make room on its shelf for an unproven product. Offering two cases for the price of one lowers the retailer's per-product cost basis, improving its profit potential on sales.

Figure 5: Trade Promotions

10. REFERENCES

- [1] Bawa, K. & Shoemaker, R.W. (1987).The effects of a direct mail coupon on brand choice behavior.*Journal of Marketing Research*. 24, 370-376
- [2] Belch EA, Belch EL. (1996), The effects of reference prices in retail advertisements. *Journal of Marketing*; 45(2), 61-69.
- [3] Belch EA, Belch EL. (1996), The effects of reference prices in retail advertisements. *Journal of Marketing*; 45, 61-69.
- [4] Blackwell, R.D., Miniard, P.W. and Engel, J.F. (2001), "Consumer Behavior", 9th ed. Fort Worth, TX: HarcourtCollege Publishers.
- [5] Blattberg RC, Neslin, S.A. (1990).*Sales Promotion, Concepts, Methods and Strategies*.New Jersey, Englewood Cliffs.Prentice Hall.
- [6] Barry Berman, Joel Evans R. (2007), —Retail Management a Strategic Approach, tenth edition Pearson Education Inc., Dorling Kindersley Publishing Inc.